

Change of Stability of Sols of Various Concentrations with their Purity.

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Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 647) have shown that when a sol of uranium ferrocyanide is coagulated with a mixture of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and KCl, the ionic antagonism is more marked in the case of the dilute sol than with a concentrated one.

It is evident from the coagulation experiments of Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) on uranium ferrocyanide sol by KCl in the presence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ that if the sol be mixed with some of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ which is a stabilising electrolyte, the sol would require more of KCl to coagulate a dilute sol than that necessary for a concentrated one, whilst the pure sol required the same amounts of KCl to coagulate the concentrated and dilute sols. In other words, if a sol contains an appreciable amount of stabilising electrolyte that gives the ion carrying the same charge as the colloid particle capable of being adsorbed by the colloid, the sol may behave abnormally on dilution towards its coagulation specially by univalent coagulating ions. This is easily explainable from the view developed by Ghosh and Dhar that the dilution effect and the behaviour towards a mixture of electrolytes are essentially connected and are mainly due to the same phenomenon of the adsorption of ions bearing the same charge as the colloid particles.

Recently Mitra and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 315) working with ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide sols containing appreciable amounts of the stabilising electrolytes, found that these sols behave abnormally towards dilution. The same authors have noted that the sol of ferric hydroxide when freed from the stabilising substance, behaves normally towards dilution.

In this paper we have investigated the sol of thorium hydroxide by peptising thorium hydroxide precipitate with thorium nitrate and then subsequent dialysis. The following results have been obtained for the coagulation of the sols of different stages of purity at their various dilutions and also by a mixture of electrolytes.

Thorium hydroxide sol.

Purity* = 1.26

Conc. of ThO ₂ .	Amount of nitrate.	Ppt. conc. of KBrO ₃ .
3.84 (g./litre)	0.963 (g./litre)	0.0531M
1.92	0.181	0.0562
0.96	0.090	0.0612

*Coagulation with mixture of KBrO₃ and K₂SO₄.*Sol conc. = 3.84 g. of ThO₂ per litre.

N/100-K ₂ SO ₄ for complete coagulation.	N/8-KBrO ₃ (c.c.)	...	0	4.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0
	Obs.	„	2.1	0	1.85	1.65	1.25	0.25
	Calc.	„	1.85	1.60	1.11	0.12
	Diff.	„	0.05	0.14	0.13

Purity = 12.2.

Conc. of ThO ₂ .	Amount of nitrate.	Ppt. conc. of KBrO ₃ .
3.84 (g./litre)	0.062 (g./litre)	0.024M
1.92	0.041	0.021
0.96	0.020	0.019

*Coagulation with mixture of KBrO₃ and K₂SO₄.*Sol conc. = 3.84 g. of ThO₂ per litre.

N/100-K ₂ SO ₄ for complete coagulation.	N/8-KBrO ₃ (c.c.)	0	1.9	0.25	0.50	1.0	1.5	
	Obs.	„	0.875	0	0.775	0.675	0.425	0.19
	Calc.	„	0.759	0.644	0.414	0.184
	Diff.	„	0.016	0.031	0.011	...

* Purity is expressed as the ratio of the molar concentrations of the colloid and its stabilising substance.

It appears, therefore, from the foregoing results that if a sol is not sufficiently pure and contains large amounts of the stabilising electrolyte, the sol may behave abnormally towards its coagulation by univalent electrolytes on dilution, inspite of the fact that additive relationship is shown when the sol is coagulated by a mixture of electrolytes.

From a study of not less than twenty five sols, Ghosh and Dhar have come to the conclusion that when a sol is coagulated by an electrolyte, such that the ions carrying the same charge as the colloid particles are not adsorbed in appreciable amounts, (a) the sol behaves normally towards dilution, (b) shows additive relationship with mixture of electrolytes, and (c) does not develop the phenomenon of acclimatisation when coagulated by the addition of an electrolyte by parts. It is, therefore, obvious that the generalisations of Ghosh and Dhar on the coagulation of sols by electrolytes would be applicable in the case of pure sols. Moreover, in one of the publications from these laboratories Gore and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 641) pointed out that considerable change in physical properties of a sol is accompanied with the degree of purity of the sol. Desai (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1928, 26, 410 ; *Current Science*, 1932, 1, 125) has shown that impure sols of some hydroxides behave abnormally on dilution towards their coagulation by KCl, LiCl, etc. When, however, the sols are purified by progressive dialysis the sols have a tendency to behave normally towards dilution when coagulated by the same univalent electrolytes. We are of opinion that this behaviour is due to the presence of sufficient quantities of stabilising electrolytes in the impure sols.

Recently Mukherjee and coworkers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 803) have investigated the stability of both positively and negatively charged manganese dioxide sols at various dilutions and report that their results are not in agreement with those obtained by Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 187). Mukherjee and coworkers find that both positively and negatively charged manganese dioxide sols require more of univalent coagulating ions to coagulate the diluted sols and at the same time additive relationships are obtained when the sols are coagulated by the mixture of ions of varying valencies.

Mukherjee and coworkers were unable to free their negatively charged manganese dioxide sol from impurities by dialysis. We have found that the proper cleaning of parchment paper for the dialysis of the sol with moderately concentrated HNO_3 is necessary

in the preparation of the sol. The decomposition of KMnO_4 , which is essentially the stabilising electrolyte, in unwashed parchment, is more and obviously renders the sol highly unstable. We have also noted that collodion bags are more suitable for dialysis than parchment bags. It is probably so, because collodion is less liable to decompose KMnO_4 than the cellulose of the parchment paper. Using these bags we have again prepared a dialysed sol of manganese dioxide (negative) which has kept its stability for over a month. The sol used by Mukherjee and coworkers was not dialysed and hence it contained sufficient free KMnO_4 and KOH .

Ghosh and Dhar prepared the positive sol of manganese dioxide by adding $N/10\text{-FeCl}_3$ solution to a litre of the dialysed negative sol, whilst Mukherjee and coworkers obtained their positive sol by adding H_2O_2 to a mixture of FeCl_3 and KMnO_4 solutions, and they have also analysed their sol. Their sol contains greater amounts of iron in comparison to the amount of manganese and they rightly conclude that their positively charged colloid of manganese dioxide may be either ferric manganate or complex solid containing different phases. We have analysed our dialysed positive sol of manganese dioxide with the following results:

Amount of total solid on evaporating 100 c.c. of the sol in a platinum crucible = 0.95 g.

Amount of Mn expressed as MnO_2 per 100 c.c. of the sol = 0.88 g.

Amount of Fe expressed as Fe_2O_3 per 100 c.c. of the sol = 0.05 g.

It is clear from the above that the amount of iron associated with manganese dioxide is considerably less and hence it is obvious that the sol obtained by Ghosh and Dhar is essentially different from that obtained by Mukherjee and coworkers. We have repeated the experiments on coagulation of dialysed sols of manganese dioxide both positive and negative, and have found that the results of Ghosh and Dhar are correct, and these sols behave normally towards dilution. We are of opinion that the results of Mukherjee and coworkers are different because of the method (*cf.* Mukherjee and Chaudhuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794) adopted by them for finding the precipitating concentrations of various electrolytes. It seems unsatisfactory to apply this method with the sols of various concentrations, which have certainly different degrees of transmission. With the coloured sols as those under investigation, it is obvious that the greater the concentration of the sol, the greater

the opacity. We have observed that these sols of MnO_2 show partial coagulation and it is evident that a sol which is already of a higher opacity may become sufficiently opaque to make the filament of the lamp invisible with a quantity of electrolyte which may not be enough to cause complete coagulation.

We have carried out the following experiments on the coagulation of both positively and negatively charged manganese dioxide sols:

(a) To 8 c.c. of the positive sol 8 c.c. of $N/200\text{-KCl}$ were added.

(b) 2 C.c. of the positive sol were made upto 8 c.c. with conductivity water and 8 c.c. of $N/200\text{-KCl}$ were added. Both the concentrated and dilute sols were kept for 10 minutes.

(c) After 10 minutes have elapsed 4 c.c. of the mixture of the concentrated sol and the electrolyte, were added to 12 c.c. of $N/400\text{-KCl}$, thus keeping the concentration of the electrolyte the same as present in the concentrated and dilute sols in (a) and (b). After 2 minutes (b) and (c) were taken in a double absorption cell and it was found with a Nutting's photometer that the extinction coefficient of (c) was less by 0.04 than that of (b). This experiment conclusively proves that the stage of coalescence is definitely greater with a diluted positive sol of manganese dioxide than with a concentrated one. Similar results were obtained with the negative sol of manganese dioxide of various dilutions.

Hence we are of opinion that the positively and negatively charged sols of manganese dioxide behave normally towards dilution when coagulated by such electrolytes as KCl , KNO_3 , K_2SO_4 , BaCl_2 , etc., and prove that the previous results of Ghosh and Dhar are correct.

CONCLUSION.

From a study of not less than twenty five sols Ghosh and Dhar have concluded that when the sol is coagulated with an electrolyte such that the ions carrying the same charge as the colloid particles is not adsorbed in appreciable amounts, (a) the sol behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by ions of varying valencies, (b) does not develop ionic antagonism, and (c) does not show the phenomenon of acclimatisation. From the experimental results it is shown that if a sol is not sufficiently pure and contains large amounts of the stabilising electrolyte, the sol may behave abnormally towards

the coagulation by univalent electrolytes on dilution inspite of the fact that additive relationship is shown when the sol is coagulated by a mixture of electrolytes.

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